

Sul Software CalSKY di Arnold Barmettler

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Una brevissima nota sul software CalSKY, software astronomico liberamente utilizzabile, sviluppato da Arnold Barmettler, Università di Zurigo e European Space Agency, e sui risultati ottenuti tramite detto software.

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CalSKY è un software astronomico, che si trova disponibile al sito <https://www.calsky.com> . E' stato usato anche in ricerche archeoastronomiche come verrà di seguito dettagliato. Innanzi tutto si riporta la voce Wikipedia, al link <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/CalSky> , che illustra quello che si può ottenere dal software.

"CalSky (sky calendar) is web-based astronomical calculator used by astronomers to plan observing. It was created by Arnold Barmettler, a researcher at the University of Zurich and formerly a scientific assistant at the European Space Agency.[1] The website, available in English and German, features a calendar (and/or email notifications) generated for your location including information on aurora, comets, tides, solar and lunar eclipses, planets, bright satellite passes (ISS, HST, etc.), occultations, transits, satellite flares, and decaying satellites that may be visible.[2][3][4]"

La pagina Wikipedia è corredata da riferimenti. Desidero aggiungere il link ad una lista delle pubblicazioni del Dr. Arnold Barmettler, Università di Zurigo <http://www.geo.uzh.ch/microsite/rsl-documents/research/SARlab/Publications/Author/BARMETTLER-A.html> .

Si desidera in particolare menzionare l'articolo, con 34 citazioni secondo Google Scholar, intitolato Geometric and Radiometric Calibration of RADARSAT Images [1], di David Small, Francesco Holecz, Erich Meier, Daniel Nüesch, and Arnold Barmettler, disponibile al link <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download?doi=10.1.1.24.4865&rep=rep1&type=pdf> .

Barmettler risulta come afferente al Remote Sensing Laboratories (RSL), University of Zürich.

Per quanto riguarda i risultati che si possono ottenere col software CalSKY, si veda l'importante osservazione ottenuta e riportata sulla pagina dell'European Space Agency. "Using Earth path predictions made by Arnold Barmettler and published on CalSKY.com, Tomáš discovered that the centreline of the narrow 4.5 kilometre-wide corridor, from where the dual transit could be viewed, passed right through the village of Stupava."

Questa frase si trova nell'articolo: Dual ISS and Venus transit viewed from Slovakia. Link https://www.esa.int/Science_Exploration/Human_and_Robotic_Exploration/International_Space_Station/Dual_ISS_and_Venus_transit_viewed_from_Slovakia

Ecco alcuni riferimenti dove il nome "Arnold Barmettler" è esplicitamente menzionato, come ricavato da Google Scholar. Si riportano le frasi che appaiono proprio con una ricerca su Scholar.

a) Sunspot Positions and Areas from Observations by Pierre Gassendi, di M Vokhmyanin, N

Zolotova - Solar Physics, 2018 - Springer ... He stated that the eclipse began at 15:40 local time, reached maximum at 16:42, and ended at 17:45. According to the calculations made in the CalSky project designed by Arnold Barmettler, the eclipse began at 15:16 local time, reached maximum at 16:26, and ended at 17:30 ... [2] .

b) From global radiance to an increased local political awareness of light pollution, LD Schuler, R Schatz, CD Berweger - Environmental science & policy, 2018 - Elsevier ... That is when artificial light switched on. A qualified colleague (reference Barmettler (nd), private communication by Arnold Barmettler) provided dusk/dawn calculations at the locations of over 50,000 accidents of the year 2012 ... [3] .

c) The eclipses in Livy's Ab Urbe Condita, AC Sparavigna - Available at SSRN 3428965, 2019 - papers.ssrn.com ... that is - in the Roman republican calendar, before the reform decided by Julius Caesar [6]. As we did in [7], for the study of the lunar eclipse of Alexander, let us use software CalSKY, a web-based astronomical calculator, created by Arnold Barmettler, University of Zurich ... [4].

d) Research on the Technological Development of GSO Small Satellite, G Jie, G Jinggang, W Zuowei... - MATEC Web of ..., 2019 - matec-conferences.org ... <https://doi.org/10.1051/mateconf/201928802003> MEAE 2019 Page 6. 7. Arnold Barmettler. Satellite found for 'MiTeX'[E13/OL]. [2013-11-09] . <http://www.calsky.com/cs.cgi.html> 8. IHS Jane's. Space Systems and Industry, Spacecraft - Defence, United States, 13-Sep-2016 ... [5] .

e) Die undulierenden Lehmziegelmauern der Spätzeit—eine disparate Forschungsgeschichte MJ Beiersdorf - 2016 - academia.edu ... CdK 13 (2010), 243–256. 30 Die nachstehenden Daten wurden mithilfe des Celestial Observer ermittelt, vgl. www.CalSky.com, Arnold Barmettler, Langnau am Albis, Schweiz (26.01.2016). 31 Angewendet auf das erste Regierungsjahr ... [6] .

Articoli che usano CalSKY sono riportati ai riferimenti [7-32]. Eccone alcuni in particolare, come dato da Google Scholar.

a) In [7] troviamo Measuring Danjon index and umbral magnitude of a partial **lunar eclipse** (July 16, 2019) C Sigismondi - arXiv preprint arXiv:1910.09291, 2019 - arxiv.org ... Applying the Argelander method as in variable stars observations (Yendell, 1905) in a scale of 5 Saturn was 0, the Moon was 1 and Jupiter 5. From calsky.com ephemerides Jupiter -2.5 and Saturn 0.1 magnitude. Then the umbral part of the Moon was $0.1 - [2.6/5] = -0.42$ mag L'autore del Rif.7 è C. Sigismondi, International Center for Relativistic Astrophysics, Roma.

b) Population size, demography and diet of the Siamese crocodile, *Crocodylus siamensis* (Schneider, 1801) in the Mesangat Swamp in Kalimantan, Indonesia. N Behler, L Kopsieker, A Staniewicz... - Raffles Bulletin of ..., 2018 ... m/s) and water temperature. **Moon phases** were recorded for the exact location with the Online Software “CalSky“(<http://www.calsky.com>) to assess whether there was a correlation with crocodile activity. A moon index was defined ... [8].

c) Visual and H-alpha measurements of solar diameter of 9 may 2016 Mercury transit C Sigismondi, H Altafi - arXiv preprint arXiv:1805.09915, 2018 - arxiv.org ... t2 11:15:23 t2 11:15:21.3(1) Tehran t1 11:11:17 t1 11:11:14.4(3) at 50.1° altitude PA=83.1° t2 11:13:58 t2 11:14:25.4(3) The **ephemerides** used are calsky.org and between parentheses 2 <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4ORAIX7iPKc> GERBERTVS vol. 11 2018 - 16 Page 4 ... [9].

d) From Data Silos to Intelligent Web for **RSO Recognition**, B Liua, L Yaoa, J Wua, Z Haob, Z Dinga - 2018 - pdfs.semanticscholar.org ... Eg, data of CelesTrack and TLE describe orbit. Data

from CEOS describe payloads. Data from NORAD Catalog, UCS Satellite and CalSky are mainly the features describing RSOs themselves ... 107 Page 6. NORAD, NASA, Calsky, and n2yo are mainly historical data ... [10].

e) **Range-Doppler mapping** of space-based targets using the JRO 50 MHz radar S Kesaraju, JD Mathews, M Milla, J Vierinen - *Earth, Moon, and Planets*, 2017 - Springer ... After an online database search (www.calsky.com), this LEO satellite was identified as the Cosmos 1626 ... 4. Fig. 4 Cosmos 1626 satellite transit path and time over JRO radar as derived from the two-line orbit elements (TLE) available from the Calsky.com online website source ... [11].

f) Diurnal and semidiurnal cyclicity of radon (²²²Rn) in **groundwater**, giardino spring, central apennines, italy MD Barberio, F Gori, M Barbieri, A Billi, R Devoti... - *Water*, 2018 - mdpi.com ... Earth tides. In particular, for the same period of the Rn and hydrogeological time series, we calculated the solid Earth tides of the study area using the CalSky—Solid Earth Tides free resource [55]. 4. Results. The Rn concentrations ... [12].

g) **Space debris** laser ranging with a 60 W single-frequency slab nanosecond green laser at 200 Hz H Zhang, M Long, H Deng, Z Wu, Z Cheng... - *Chinese Optics ...*, 2019 - osapublishing.org ... Space-Track.org/, with range errors at hundreds to thousands of meters. The debris names can be found at <http://www.calsky.com/cs.cgi/Satellite/>. With the above configuration of the proposed SLR system, the space debris was measured ... [13].

Si è voluto riportare alcuni dei riferimenti da Google Scholar con più dettaglio, per mostrare l'utilizzo multidisciplinare del software CalSKY.

Conclusion

Taluni potrebbero pensare che i software astronomici disponibili in rete non siano stati sviluppati da astronomi. In questo caso specifico, ossia CalSKY, il software è stato sviluppato da un docente dell'Università di Zurigo che ha lavorato presso l'ESA. Tale software ha dimostrato, con l'osservazione sperimentale del transito di Venere e della stazione IIS, la sua altissima qualità. Il suo utilizzo in campo come quello archeoastronomico, ad esempio, è quindi più che ben fondato. Come mostrato dai diversi riferimenti riportati, l'uso di CalSKY è stato fondamentale per varie ricerche multidisciplinari. Per quanto riguarda un altro software ampiamente usato, Stellarium, una analoga nota sarà a breve pubblicata.

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